

DEVELOPMENT OF DAMAGE IN COMPOSITES UNDER THERMOMECHANICAL LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work was to develop a predictive capability for the onset of ply failure in composite laminates subjected to combined thermal and mechanical loads. The material systems studied were carbon fiber-reinforced toughened epoxy and bismaleimide composites, IM7/977-3 and IM7/5250-4. Thermomechanical properties required for residual stress estimation were obtained from tests on unidirectional laminates. These laminates were tested at 23°C and -196 °C. Coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) were measured using strain gages, over the temperature range of 149 °C to -196 °C (liquid nitrogen). Laminates, [0/90₂/0]_T, [0/90₃/0]_T, [0₂/90₂]_S, [±30/90]_S, and [0/±45/90]_S were used to experimentally determine the initiation of microcracks in the 90° plies. The onset of microcracking was detected from acoustic emission and incremental loading and unloading experiments, and confirmed from microscopic examination of polished specimen edges. Ply stresses were calculated for the corresponding conditions from laminated plate theory, using the appropriate experimentally generated thermomechanical properties and applied load. Transverse tensile strength increased at lower temperatures, while strain to failure decreased (indicating increased brittleness). The stress level at the onset of microcracking decreased significantly at lower temperatures, mainly due to an increase in the curing residual stresses. Lamination theory in conjunction with the maximum stress failure criterion tends to overestimate the onset of the microcracking in the laminates considered.

Key Words: carbon fiber, toughened epoxy, bismaleimide, cryogenic, microcracking, residual stress

INTRODUCTION

Advanced polymer composites are being explored for structural applications at extremely low temperatures [1]. Exposure to these cryogenic temperatures can cause ply microcracking in these composites due to thermal residual stresses that arise from the anisotropy in the composite ply coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). Transverse ply cracking often provides a pathway for the ingress of moisture or corrosive chemicals; in cryotanks, transverse cracking can cause leakage of the pressurized liquid fuel. Very little work has been reported in the technical literature [2-4] on the mechanical performance and damage development in polymer composites at cryogenic temperatures. The objective of this work was to investigate the initiation and progress of damage in composite laminates at cryogenic temperatures. The material systems investigated were carbon fiber-reinforced toughened epoxy and bismaleimide composites, IM7/977-3 and IM7/5250-4. The thermomechanical properties required for the analysis were obtained from tests on unidirectional laminates. These laminates were tested at 23 °C and -196 °C using a cryogenic chamber installed on a mechanical testing machine. Three cross-ply laminates and two quasi-isotropic laminates were used to experimentally determine the onset of microcracking under combined mechanical and thermal loads. Microcracking was detected from acoustic emission, and incremental loading and unloading, and confirmed from microscopic examination of polished specimen

edges. Ply stresses were calculated for the corresponding conditions from laminated plate theory, using the appropriate experimentally generated thermomechanical properties and the applied load. The calculated total stress (curing residual stress and mechanical stress) in the 90 degree ply was compared with the experimentally determined transverse strength at each corresponding temperature.

EXPERIMENT

Unidirectional and multidirectional laminate panels were laid up from the unitape prepreg and were cured in an autoclave in accordance with the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The IM7/BMI panels were post cured. The $[0]_{8T}$, $[90]_{8T}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates were used to determine thermomechanical properties at cryogenic temperatures that are required for analytical calculation. Three cross-ply laminates, $[0/90_2/0]_T$, $[0/90_3/0]_T$, $[0_2/90_2]_S$, and two quasi-isotropic laminates, $[30/-30/90]_S$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ were used to investigate the onset of microcracking at 23 °C and -196 °C. All specimens were 1.52 cm wide with a gage length of 15.2 cm due to limitations imposed by the test fixture used in cryogenic test. No end-tabs were used for specimens tested at all temperatures. Strain gages were used to record specimen strains at all test temperatures. The edges of the specimens for the multidirectional laminate specimens were first ground with sandpaper and then polished with 5-micron and 1-micron polishing powder to enhance microscopic imaging for crack detection. Prior to testing, all specimen edges were examined under a microscope to determine if specimen cutting and handling induced any damage. No damage was observed in any specimen prior to testing. All specimens were stored in a desiccated cabinet until test.

A special mechanical grip (18 KN load capacity) was designed and built for tests at cryogenic temperatures. The clamping face of each grip was coated using a Surfalloy process to enhance the gripping action without damaging the specimen surface by grip force. All specimens were tested on an MTS test machine using a stainless-steel container, designed and built in-house, for tests at liquid nitrogen temperature (-196 °C). Specimens were mounted on the test machine and cooled to the desired test temperature by immersion in liquid nitrogen in the insulated stainless-steel container and allowed to equilibrate for 10 minutes. They were then loaded in tension at a strain rate of 0.02/min. Figure 1 shows the mechanical test setup at liquid nitrogen temperature.

Unidirectional panels measuring 7.5 cm x 7.5 cm were prepared to determine the coefficients of thermal expansion that are required to calculate the residual stresses. Composite CTEs were measured using strain gages with a 6.35 mm gage length. Two longitudinal and two transverse strain gages were mounted on each specimen with a high-temperature adhesive and cured as recommended by the manufacturer. Ultra-low-expansion titanium silicate was used as the reference material for completion of the strain gage bridge circuit. The thermal strain measurement system used can accommodate eight channels; one was used for time, one for temperature and the remaining six for collecting thermal strain data. Specimens were cycled between -130 °C and 150 °C at a rate of 3 °C/min, and held isothermally for 10 min after each 20 °C increment of temperature in a computer-controlled temperature chamber. Because of low-temperature limitations of the temperature chamber, specimens were immersed in liquid nitrogen and held for 20 min. A software program controlled test parameters and continuous acquisition of temperature and strain data during both heating and cooling cycles. The CTE was obtained from a linear fit to the data over the entire test temperature range. The resolution of strain and temperature measurement with this experimental set-up is less than 1×10^{-6} and 0.5 °C, respectively. The correction for transverse sensitivity of the strain gage was made for the longitudinal strain using the transverse sensitivity of the strain gage provided by the manufacturer.

ANALYTICAL BACKGROUND

The analytical model developed by Hahn and Pagano [5,6] in conjunction with the classical laminated plate theory was used to calculate the residual stresses resulting from cure. The residual stresses σ_i^R in each ply can be written as

$$\sigma_i^R = Q_{ij}A_{jk}^{-1}N_k^T - Q_{ij}e_j^T \quad (1)$$

where

Q_{ij} = reduced stiffnesses at the final temperature of interest

A_{ij} = laminate stiffnesses

N_k^T = stress resultants due to thermal strains

e_j^T = ply thermal strains measured from the stress-free state

The specimens chosen in the present work are cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates subjected to the uniaxial loading in the 0-degree direction. Since the 90-degree plies are the weakest under the loading conditions, we only need to calculate the stresses in the 90 degree plies. The total stress, σ^T in the 90° ply can be given by

$$\sigma_i^T = Q_{ij}A_{jk}^{-1}N_k + \sigma_i^R \quad (2)$$

The σ^T in the 90° ply was calculated at the onset of microcracking using a commercially available code ASCA [7] and compared with the experimentally determined 90-degree laminate strength at the corresponding temperatures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The thermoelastic properties of unidirectional lamina required in the analysis are determined at 23 °C and –196 °C and are given in Table 1. There is a considerable variation in modulus and strength in matrix-dominated orientations (transverse and shear) for both material systems over the temperature range of 23 to –196 °C, whereas the longitudinal modulus and Poisson's ratio remained unchanged. Figures 2a and 2b show the representative transverse and shear stress-strain curves for the IM7/977-3 composite. The non-linearity of the shear stress-strain decreased significantly at –196 °C as shown in Figure 2b. The similar stress-strain behavior was also observed for the IM7/5250-4 composite.

An acoustic emission technique (AE) is employed to detect the onset of microcracking in this work. When a sudden acoustic emission event was observed, the specimen was unloaded and examined under a microscope to confirm the presence of microcracks. Figures 3a and 3b show the acoustic emission record for the IM7/977-3, $[0_2/90_2]_S$ specimens tested at 23 °C and –196 °C, respectively, indicating the first occurrence of microcracking in a form of transverse crack. It should be noted that no other acoustic events were recorded in Figure 3a, indicating no presence of ambient noise during the test at room temperature, whereas continuous presence of low level acoustic emission signals exhibited throughout the test as background noise possibly due to the boiling of liquid nitrogen as shown in Figure 3b. The large size of the AE signal near the end indicates the onset of microcracking and can be easily distinguishable from the background noise. The onset of the microcracking was confirmed using a microscope after unloading. If no microcracking was found under microscopic examination, then the specimen was incrementally loaded to either occurrence of acoustic emission signal above the background noise level or the prescribed load. This procedure continued until there was a physical presence of microcracks.

Figure 3 shows micrographs of the transverse cracks at 23°C and -196 °C. All the microcracking observed on the specimen edge extended through the entire thickness of the 90° plies as shown in Figure 3(a) and 3(b). There was a one-to-one mapping of cracks on both edges of the same specimen, suggesting that these transverse cracks traversed the full specimen width. In specimens tested at -196°C, a slanted partial crack was also observed near the major crack (Figure 3b); this type of damage was not observed in specimens tested at 23°C. The stress in the 90° plies of all laminates at the onset of microcracking, was calculated from the applied stress using classical laminated plate theory for comparison with the transverse strength obtained from tensile tests on [90]_{8T} specimens. The curing residual stress was calculated with the stress-free temperature assumed as indicated in Table 1. This assumption is based on the fact that the toughened epoxy and bismaleimide exhibit stress relaxation during the isothermal holding in cure. Table 2 shows the 90° ply stresses calculated for all the laminates at the onset of transverse cracking and the measured composite transverse strength. In all cases except for the IM7/977-3 [$\pm 30/90$]_S and [0/ $\pm 45/90$]_S laminates at 23°C, the total 90° ply stress calculated at the onset of microcracking is 4% to 20% greater than the transverse strength determined by test using the [90]_{8T} specimens. A number of factors are considered as the sources of this discrepancy in Table 2.

The *in situ* off-axis strength in a composite laminate generally differs by a various degree from the strength determined using a typical unidirectional coupon (8 plies or 12 plies) specimen. It is believed to be due to size effect as well as constraint effect of the adjacent plies. The amount of constraint among the laminates involved is considerably different from one another. Experimental uncertainties such as thermomechanical properties, stress free temperature, determination of stress level at onset of microcracking at -196°C are also considered to be one of main contribution to the discrepancy.

CONCLUSIONS

Experiments were conducted to determine the influence of cryogenic temperatures on the onset of microcracking for IM7/977-3 and IM7/5250-4 composite laminates. Based on the results, the following conclusions are drawn.

- Transverse tensile and shear strengths and moduli increased at -196°C compared with 23 °C while strain to failure decreased.
- The nonlinearity of the shear stress-strain curve decreased significantly at lower temperatures.
- The stress level at the onset of transverse cracking decreased at -196°C, mainly due to an increase in the curing residual stresses.
- Lamination theory in conjunction with the maximum stress failure criterion tends to overestimate the onset of the transverse cracking in this laminate.

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Table 1 Thermoelastic properties of IM7/977-3 and IM7/5250-4 composites

Property	IM7/977-3		IM7/5250-4	
	Temperature, °C	23	-196	23
Longitudinal modulus, GPa	172	172	172	172
Transverse modulus, GPa	9.7	11.7	10.5	12.1
Shear modulus, GPa	6.1	9.2	5.5	9.0
Poisson's ratio	0.33	0.33	0.36	0.36
Longitudinal CTE, 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	0.18	0.18	0.25	0.25
Transverse CTE, 10 ⁻⁶ /°F	23.4	20.3	24.7	21.1
Transverse Tensile strength, MPa	74.5	97.2	84.0	93.8
Shear strength, MPa	113.3	132.0	97.8	121
Curing stress free temperature	163		232	

Table 2. Summary of onset of microcracking

Laminate	Temperature °C	Stress at Onset of microcracking MPa	Stresses in 90° ply, MPa			Measured 90 ply strength MPa
			Curing residual stress	Mechanical stress	Total stress	
IM7/977-3						
[0/90 ₂ /0] _T	23	566	29	58	87	75
	-196.00	412	75	42	117	97
[0 ₂ /90 ₂] _S	23.00	567	29	58	87	75
	-196.00	409	75	42	117	97
[0/90 ₃ /0] _T	23.00	442	28	55	83	75
	-196.00	342	74	43	117	97
[30/-30/90] _S	23.00	245	29	31	60	75
	-196.00	224	75	29	104	97
[0/±45/90] _S	23	283	29	37	66	75
	-196	173	75	22	97	97
IM7/5250-4						
[0/±45/90] _S	23	275	47	40	87	84
	-196	153	87	22	109	94

Figure 1. Test setup at liquid nitrogen temperature; test specimen immersed in the white stainless steel container.

Figure 2. Stress-strain curves for IM7/977-3 composite laminate

(a) 23 °C

(b) -196 °C

Figure 3. Acoustic emission record indicating the onset of microcracking for IM7/977-3 $[0_2/90_2]_S$

(a) 23°C

(b) -196°C

Figure 4. Micrographs showing the onset of microcracking for IM7/977-3 $[0_2/90_2]_S$